

GEOGRAPHICAL SCIENCES

ENDANGERED SPECIES OF SHEKI-ZAGATALA NATURE

Nazarova G.

Azerbaijan Tourism and Management University, PhD student

Baku, Azerbaijan

ORCID: 0000-0002-5870-7397

ABSTRACT

As in many parts of the world, in the Sheki-Zagatala region, the threat of extinction of living things is always on the agenda. The article examines the endangered flora and fauna of the Sheki-Zagatala region. Living things are either extinct and listed in the Red Book, or face this threat. Taking this into account, the article examines the effect of the destruction of the flora and fauna of the region on ecotourism and suggests measures to prevent it.

Keywords: Sheki-Zagatala, plants, animals, endangered species, ecotourism.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the Science Development Foundation under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan - Grant № EIF-GAT-6-2021-2(39)-13/05/2-M-05.

1. INTRODUCTION

The flora and fauna of the earth is rich. Their distribution is based on the ecological environment of the countries where they are located. At present, the issue of extinction of plants and animals, which is accelerating in different regions of the world, is relevant. Extinction is a normal part of the evolutionary process. However, the rapid progress of this process causes great losses for our planet. In general, the plants and animals die due to problems in the ecological environment. These problems are usually formed as a result of natural events and anthropogenic influence. These include air, land and water pollution. Of course, these lead to the destruction of plants, animals, including mammals, reptiles, amphibians, and birds and etc.

This problem is also on the agenda in the Republic of Azerbaijan. The main goal of the article is to investigate the impact of the endangered species of the Sheki-Zagatala region on the ecological environment, including the ecotourism sector. The object of the article is the endangered species of plants and animals of the Sheki-Zagatala region. The subject of the article is to examine the current situation of the Sheki-Zagatala region based on this problem and its solutions.

2. GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE WORLD'S ENDANGERED SPECIES

Earth's ecosystem is divided into living and non-living. The living beings that form the basis of the biosphere consist of humans, animals and plants. The living creatures were spread over the world due to the natural conditions such as geographical environment, climate, soil cover. For example, some animals hibernate in winter or spring due to these conditions.

The death of animals in the zoo world causes big problems. As an example, these can be shown:

❖ In the Middle Ages in Europe, the number of mice increased by killing cats, and as a result, a plague spread;

❖ Due to the spread of bird flu, the number of poultry decreased and as a result the number of ticks increased;

❖ In the 1950s, DDT (dichloro diphenyl trichloroethane, a highly toxic and persistent insecticide) was used against mosquitoes in the fight against malaria in Borneo, Indonesia. This DDT also caused the death of insects, which are the enemies of caterpillars. As a result, the caterpillars multiplied, ate the thatched roofs and caused the houses to collapse. Both lizards and cats died due to DDT, and as a result, mice multiplied. After that, a cholera epidemic began to spread on the island;

❖ In one area in Nigeria, rhinoceroses were killed because they were damaging corn fields. For several years in a row there had been plenty of corn in the fields. However, at that time, fish species in rivers and lakes suddenly decreased and began to become extinct. The reason for this was that rhino poo was useful as a fertilizer for the plants (phytoplankton), which were necessary for the zooplankton (small animals) that formed the food source of the fish. The destruction or removal of rhinos from the area has led to the reduction of vegetation in the river, the loss of food sources for fish and the death of fish and etc.

In general, the flora and fauna of the world are diverse. These are directly related to natural conditions. So, the flora and fauna of countries located in different climate zones, as well as their characteristic features, are slightly different from plants and animals living in other geographical areas. For example, foxes living in the arctic region are more cold-resistant than foxes living in the steppes, they have fat and fat bodies, and the overall body structure is partially different.

From here it is known that plants and animals adapt to their environment and have important genetic differences from a morphological point of view. Also, plants are food for animals, and insects are food for birds, fish, and reptiles. This method goes like this. In other words, the existence of plants and animals is the main source of food for other living things. This is a kind of chain organization of the food of living creatures (Yazıcı, 2019, 2; Türkoğlu and Verdiyeva, 2019).

So, protecting the living environment is a very important issue. This is an important issue for the health of our ecological environment, as well as for a better

future. In general, the process of protecting endangered species can be divided into three stages:

- 1) identification - identification of species facing the threat of extinction of the population of the species;
- 2) protection - preparation and implementation of short-term measures to prevent the species from becoming extinct;
- 3) recovery – preparation and implementation of long-term measures for the recovery of species without facing the threat of extinction (Wilcove, 2010, 220).

For a long time, the countries of the world have been taking special measures and making decisions for the protection of flora and fauna:

- There are many national parks, animal reserve areas and fossil reserve areas under protection by UNESCO with the Convention on the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage signed on 16 November 1972. As an example, these can be shown: Iguazu National Park (Argentina), Belize Barrier Reef Reserve System (Belize), Dinosaur State Park (Canada), Morne Trois Piton National Park (Dominican Republic), Great Himalayan National Park and Preserve (India), Mount Kenya National Park, and Natural Forest (Kenya), Okapi Wildlife Reserve (Democratic Republic of the Congo), Rio Platano Biosphere Reserve (Honduras), Monarch Butterfly Biosphere Reserve (Mexico), Tasmania Wildlands (Australia), Mount Hamiguitan Wildlife Sanctuary (Philippines). Two heritage sites have been removed from the UNESCO World Heritage List because they were previously taken under protection and could not be adequately protected by the relevant countries. One of them, Arabian Oryx Sanctuary, aimed to protect animal generations. However, it was determined that it was reduced by 90% without permission by the Oman state; It has been deleted from the UNESCO heritage list due to the reduction of species diversity and encouraging poaching;
- 1950 – International Convention for the Protection of Birds;
- 1979 – Convention for the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats;
- 1987 – European Convention for the Protection of Pets;
- 1991– United Nations Convention on Biodiversity;
- 1994 – Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Plants and Animals;
- The International Union for Conservation of Nature created the “The International Union for Conservation of Nature's Red List of Threatened Species - IUCN”;
- October 4th is Animal Day and has been universally celebrated since 1931 (Yazıcı, 2019, 2-3).

3. STATE POLICY FOR THE PROTECTION OF ENDANGERED SPECIES IN THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN

Azerbaijan is a country rich in flora and fauna. Nevertheless, in our Republic, as in many countries of the world, its species are in danger of extinction. It is in this direction that important steps have been taken in our Republic. In this case, the successful policy of The National Leader of the Azerbaijani Nation Heydar Aliyev, his successor and President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev, and First Lady Mehriban Aliyeva is commendable. In Azerbaijan, orders and decrees have been issued and laws have been adopted for this matter:

- March 27, 1998 – Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on fishing;
- June 4, 1999 – Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the animal world;
- October 28, 1999 – Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on joining the European Convention “On the Protection of European Wildlife and Natural Environment”;
- March 14, 2000 – Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on joining the International Convention “On Plant Protection”;
- July 15, 2000 – Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan on approval of the Regulation on the “Red Book” of the Republic of Azerbaijan;
- March 24, 2006 – Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the approval of the National Strategy and Action Plan for the protection and sustainable use of biological diversity in the Republic of Azerbaijan;
- December 26, 2008 – Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the establishment of a zoological park;
- January 7, 2009 – Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the approval of the “Rules for regulating the international trade of endangered species of wild fauna and wild flora”;
- March 27, 2020 – Regulation on the Biological Diversity Protection Service under the Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of the Republic of Azerbaijan and etc. (<https://e-qanun.az>; <http://eco.gov.az>).

4. RARE, ENDANGERED AND VULNERABLE SPECIES IN THE SHEKI-ZAGATALA NATURE

As in other regions of Azerbaijan, the flora and fauna of the Sheki-Zagatala economic geographical region are diverse. Nevertheless, there are also species in danger of extinction in the region.

Figure 1. Rount-leaved Wintergreen (Mammadov et al, 2012, 212)

As an example, these can be shown: Agasyllis, Caucasus belladonna, boxwood, sweet chestnut, cladochaeta, turkish hazel, Alpine corydalis, houns tongue, alexandrian laurel, date plum, scarlet firethorn, ivy, gentian, stinking Juniper, cherry laurel, Caucasian Lily, violet limodore, peony, wing nut, rount-leaved Wintergreen, Oriental plane tree, primose, Persian ironwood tree, Caucasian pine, pseudovesicaria, pomegranate, snow rose, brier, yellow azalea, Caucasian houseleek,

bladdernut, autumn daffodil, common yellow, stoat, Caucasian parsley frog, Greek tortoise, rosalia longicorn, agreeable caterpillar hunter, heart-leaved ox eye, wild wine, valerian, Alpine woodsia, white-eyed bream, apollo, wood nymph, bumblebee, Caucasian grouse, Caucasian snowcock, Eastern imperial eagle, chamois, leopard, striped hyena, lynx, Africal wildcat and etc. (Mammadov et al, 2012, 212- 215).

Figure 2. Caucasian houseleek (Mammadov et al, 2012, 213)

5. ENDANGERED SPECIES OF THE SHEKI-ZAGATALA REGION AND ECO TOURISM

It is clear that there are certain ecological problems in the Sheki-Zagatala region, as in any region. This leads to the destruction of rare and living examples

of nature. Protection of hydrological monuments of the region, preservation of nature, continuous greening works, creation of objects providing ecological protection such as reserves and sanctuaries are big steps to protect the bio and zoo world of Sheki-Zagatala region.

Figure 3. Apollon (Mammadov et al, 2012, 215)

Ecology directly affects the ecotourism sector. Also, nature directly affects ecotourism, as living beings are the basis of ecology. They are the main wealth of the living nature of Sheki-Zagatala region. They are the main wealth of the living nature of Sheki-Zagatala region. Each of the endangered species are creatures that enrich the Sheki-Zagatala ecotourism. It is the strengthening of measures to prevent their extinction, their restoration and reproduction that can lead to the enrichment of our ecotourism. As a result, natural beauties are the center of attention of ecotourists (Nazarova, 2022a, 3-8; Nazarova, 2022b, 8-11; Nazarova, 2022c, 21-25).

6. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

As a result, in Sheki-Zagatala region, like in every region of the world, natural creatures are in danger. Protecting the ecosystem and taking measures on this basis will have a positive effect on the protection of the environment, as well as the ecotourism of the region. Living creatures are the main objects of interest for tourists in the field of ecotourism. It is precisely this that increases the interest of tourists in the region. For this reason, we mention our recommendations below:

✓ It is appropriate to educate the students, local residents, and the public about endangered species of the Sheki-Zagatala region;

✓ At the moment, measures are being taken to express the importance of the natural creatures of the region for our ecology. It would be even better to strengthen these works. For example, showing video instructions, preparing television programs, publishing materials on the internet, organizing scientific seminars or conferences, etc.;

✓ It is important to conduct environmental education to inform the local population and tourists visiting the place about anthropogenic effects on plants and animals.

References

1. Azərbaycan ekoturizm potensialı / Məmmədov Q., Yusifov E., Xəlilov M., Kərimov V. – Bakı: Şərq-Qərb, I cild. – 2012. – 360 s. (Mammadov G., Yusifov E., Xalilov M., Karimov V. (2012). Azerbaijan: ecotourism potential. volume I, Sharg-Garb, Baku)

2. Azərbaycan Respublikasında bioloji müxtəlifliyinin qorunması və davamlı istifadəsinə dair Milli Stratejiya və Fəaliyyət Planının təsdiq edilməsi haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin Sərəncamı (Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the approval of the National Strategy and Action Plan for the protection and sustainable use of biological diversity in the Republic of Azerbaijan) 11.08.2022. Retrieved from <https://e-qanun.az/framework/11513>

3. Azərbaycan Respublikasının Ekologiya və Təbii Sərvətlər Nazirliyi yanında Bioloji Müxtəlifliyin Qorunması Xidməti haqqında Əsasnamə (Regulation on the Biological Diversity Protection Service under the Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of the Republic of Azerbaijan) 11.08.2022. Retrieved from <http://eco.gov.az/index.php?ln=az&pg=635>

4. Azərbaycan Respublikasının “Qırmızı Kitabı” haqqında Əsasnamənin təsdiq edilməsi barədə Azərbaycan Respublikasının Nazirlər Kabineti Qərarı (Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the approval of the Regulation on the “Red Book” of the Republic of Azerbaijan) 12.08.2022. Retrieved from <https://e-qanun.az/framework/725>

5. “Avropanın canlı təbiətinin və təbii mühitinin qorunması haqqında” Avropa Konvensiyasına qoşulmaq barədə Azərbaycan Respublikasının qanunu (Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on joining the European Convention “On the Protection of European Wildlife and Natural Environment”) 12.08.2022. Retrieved from <https://e-qanun.az/framework/2986>

6. Balıqçılıq haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikasının qanunu (Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on fishing). 11.08.2022. Retrieved from <https://e-qanun.az/framework/3523>

7. “Bitki mühafizəsi haqqında” Beynəlxalq Konvensiyaya qoşulmaq barədə Azərbaycan Respublikasının qanunu (Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on joining the International Convention “On Plant Protection”) 12.08.2022. Retrieved from <https://e-qanun.az/framework/648>

8. Heyvanlar aləmi haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikasının qanunu (Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the animal world).12.08.2022. Retrieved from <https://e-qanun.az/framework/3850>

9. “Kökünün kəsilməsi təhlükəsi olan vəhşi fauna və yabanı flora növlərinin beynəlxalq ticarətinin tənzimlənməsi Qaydaları”nın təsdiq edilməsi haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikasının Nazirlər Kabineti Qərarı (Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the approval of the “Rules for regulating the international trade of endangered species of wild fauna and wild flora”). 11.08.2022. Retrieved from <https://e-qanun.az/framework/16045>

10. Nazarova G. (2022a). Ecological problems of hydrological monuments of Sheki-Zagatala region. International independent scientific journal, №40, The Republic of Poland, 3-8, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6813297>. 12.07.2022. Retrieved from http://www.iis-journal.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/IISJ_40.pdf

11. Nazarova G. (2022b). Importance of the ecological environment of the north-western region of Azerbaijan. Annali d’Italia № 30, Vol 2, Florence, Italy, 8-11. 26.05.2022. Retrieved from <http://www.itadiana.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Annali-d%E2%80%99Italia-%E2%84%9630-part-2-2022.pdf>

12. Nazarova G. (2022c). The importance of nature reserves and sanctuaries in the Sheki-Zagatala region in the development of ecotourism. Annali d’Italia № 33, Florence, Italy, 21-25. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6907596>. 26.05.2022. Retrieved from <http://www.itadiana.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Annali-d%E2%80%99Italia-%E2%84%9633-2022.pdf>

13. Türkoğlu M., Verdiyeva V. (2019). Biyoçeşitliliğin ve ekosistemin devamlığı. 07.08.2022. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332767045_BIYOCESITLIGIN_VE_EKOSISTEMIN_DEVAMLIGI

14. Yazıcı, Ö. (2019). Hayvan Koruma Farkındalığı Açısından Zoocoğrafya Öğretimine Yönelik Öğrenci Görüşlerinin İncelenmesi (Investigation of the student views' on zoogeographical teaching in terms of animal protection awareness). *International Journal of Geography and Geography Education (IGGE)* № 40, 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.32003/iggei.544468>. 06.08.2022. Retrieved from <https://dergipark.org.tr/pub/igge/issue/47105/544468>

15. Zooloji parkın yaradılması haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin Sərəncamı

(Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the establishment of a zoological park). 11.08.2022. Retrieved from <https://e-qanun.az/framework/15987>

16. Wilcove, David S. (2010). *Conservation Biology for All*. Edit by Navjot S. Sodhi & Paul R. Ehrlich. Endangered species management: the US experience. (220-235). New York, Oxford University Press Inc. 08.08.2022. Retrieved from https://conbio.org/images/content_publications/ConservationBiologyforAll_reducedsize.pdf